

Tris-Complexes of Morpholine with Copper(II) Carboxylates

N. KUMAR and A. K. SURI

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 001

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1 : 3 Adducts of copper(II) carboxylates with morpholine of composition $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2 \cdot 3 \text{Morph}$ where R is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$ -p, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$ -p, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}$ -p and $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ and Morph is morpholine have been isolated. The complexes are non-electrolytes as shown by conductance measurements. Molecular weight determinations, magnetic moments and spectral measurements indicate that the complexes are dimeric of formula $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_4 \cdot 2 \text{Morph}]_2 \cdot 4 \text{Morph}$. The excess morpholine molecules are regarded to be present in the hollow spaces of the solid crystals. Infrared spectra suggest that morpholine coordinates to copper through nitrogen.

LOW magnetic moments and anomalous paramagnetic behaviour of complexes of copper(II) carboxylates have generated considerable interest in their studies and a large number of their adducts have been prepared with nitrogen and other donor molecules with a view to investigate the effect of the coordinated ligand on the magnetic properties of the parent copper(II) carboxylate^{1,2}. Although a large number of adducts of various nitrogen donors have been studied but no work has been done on complexes of morpholine with these systems except some of its 1 : 1 and/or 1 : 2 complexes with copper(II) carboxylates^{3,4}. In the present communication we now report preparation and characterization of some 1 : 3 complexes of morpholine with copper(II) carboxylates of *p*-toluic, *p*-chloro-benzoic, *p*-hydroxybenzoic and phenylacetic acids.

Experimental

Materials Used :

Copper(II) carboxylates were prepared by standard published methods⁵. The purity of the samples was established by metal analysis. Morpholine (BDH) was purified by fractional distillation and was stored over potassium hydroxide pellets.

Preparation of Complexes :

Copper(II) p-toluate morpholine complex : A large excess of morpholine was added to a 0.25 M solution of copper(II) *p*-toluate in acetone. A blue coloured solution was obtained which on standing deposited a blue crystalline compound. It was separated, washed with acetone and dried in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide.

Copper(II) p-chlorobenzoate morpholine complex :

A solution of morpholine in acetone was added in 1 : 4 molar ratio to a suspension of copper(II) *p*-chlorobenzoate in acetone. The reaction mixture on refluxing gave a clear blue solution. It was filtered and allowed to stand. The blue crystalline compound deposited was separated and dried as described above.

Adducts of copper(II) *p*-hydroxybenzoate and phenylacetate with morpholine were prepared by a similar procedure in methanol and dry ether respectively.

Copper in these complexes was estimated gravimetrically as cuprous thiocyanate. C and H analyses were carried out in the micro-analytical laboratory of this department. Conductance measurements were carried out on $10^{-3}M$ solutions in methanol using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge Type CL 01/02. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene. Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra were recorded in chloroform or benzene solutions on Beckman DK-2A UV VIS Near IR Spectrophotometer in the range 28,500-12,500 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra over the range 4,000-200 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Perkin Elmer double beam IR Spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The complexes isolated are dark blue or purple in colour, soluble in common organic solvents like acetone, methanol and benzene and are stable in air except copper(II) phenylacetate complex which decomposes to a blue residue on prolonged standing.

Elemental analyses (Table-1) suggest that the complexes may be assigned a general formula $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2 \cdot 3\text{Morph}$. Conductance values in methanol fall in the range 21 to 26 $\text{mole}^{-1} \text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ (Table-2) indicating that the complexes are non-ionic. Molecular weights (Table-2) which could be determined only in two cases show that the complexes are dimeric in solution.

figuration⁴. In methanol band II is not observed, as expected.

In the infrared spectra two bands in the NH stretching regions are observed at 3340 cm^{-1} and $3150\text{-}3210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at 3340 cm^{-1} is the same as observed in free morpholine and can be

 TABLE-1 SOME PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_4 \cdot 2\text{Morph}] \cdot 4\text{Morph}$ COMPLEXES

R	Colour	Yield %	Elements Analyses %					
			Found			Calculated		
			Cu	C	H	Cu	C	H
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{-p}$	Dark blue	82	10.60	55.95	6.30	10.68	56.48	6.89
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-p}$	Dark blue	64	9.82	49.00	6.00	9.99	49.06	5.50
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH-p}$	Purple	69	10.42	52.20	6.50	10.61	52.09	6.18
$\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	Purple	53	10.60	56.00	7.00	10.68	56.48	6.89

 TABLE-2 MOLECULAR WEIGHT, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_4 \cdot 2\text{Morph}] \cdot 4\text{Morph}$ COMPLEXES

R	Molecular Weight		Molar Conductance ($\text{mole}^{-1} \text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$)	Magnetic Data		Electronic Spectral Data	
	Found	Required*		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Temp. (°K)	Band I cm^{-1}	Band II cm^{-1}
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{-p}$	1104	1189.8	24.3 ^a	1.68	294	13,160 ^a 13,340 ^b	- 23,990 ^b
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-p}$	1163	1271.8	22.4 ^a	1.71	295	13,090 ^a 13,790 ^b	- 24,930 ^b
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH-p}$	-	1197.8	26.3 ^a	1.67	296	13,120 ^a	-
$\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	-	1189.8	21.4 ^a	1.64	296	13,500 ^a 13,660 ^c	- 24,840 ^c

*Required for dimeric formula
 a=Methanol
 b=Chloroform
 c= Benzene

Magnetic moments of the addition complexes fall in the range 1.64-1.71 B.M. (Table-2) which are less than the values of 1.72-1.82 B.M. generally observed in copper(II) compounds with strong covalent bonds. This indicates that the present complexes are dinuclear carboxylate bridged species of the type $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_4 \cdot 2\text{Morph}] \cdot 4\text{Morph}$ in which lowering of the magnetic moments takes place due to spin-spin coupling occurring between the two contiguous copper(II) ions of the dimeric species. The excess four uncoordinated morpholine molecules are believed to occupy hollow spaces present in the solid crystals of the dimeric adduct molecules. The electronic spectra of the complexes in non-polar solvents invariably show two bands centred around $13,500$ and $24,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ similar to the bands I & II generally observed in dinuclear carboxylate bridged complexes which further confirm their binuclear con-

assigned to NH stretching vibration of uncoordinated morpholine while the band at $3150\text{-}3210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to NH stretching vibration of coordinated morpholine. A slight positive shift of $10\text{-}20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed in COC stretching vibration of the coordinated morpholine further confirms its coordination through nitrogen atom⁶. The difference between the asymmetric and symmetric COO stretching frequencies in the present complexes works up more than 200 cm^{-1} (Table-3) suggesting that carboxylate group is behaving as a syn-syn bridging ligand⁷.

Some additional bands observed in the far infrared spectra of the complexes over the range $350\text{-}300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been tentatively assigned to Cu-N stretching vibrations in conformity with the observations made by earlier workers⁸.

TABLE—3 INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) of $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_4 \cdot 2\text{MORPH}] \cdot 4\text{MORPH}$ COMPLEXES

R	$\nu(\text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{COO})$			$\nu(\text{COC})$	$\nu(\text{Cu-N})$
		asym*	sym	Asym-Sym		
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{-p}$	3352 3209	1598	1375	223	1114	338
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-p}$	3350 3210	1602	1375	227	1104	345 313
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH-p}$	3342 3152	1593	1385	208	1115	312
$\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	3351 3150	1586	1372	214	1109	344
Morph	3340				1095	

*Main band observed in the asymmetric region.

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